

CULTURE, SUBCULTURE, COUNTERCULTURE: DEFINITION AND BOUNDARIES OF CONCEPTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15447928>

Abstract. *The analysis and comparison of the concepts of culture, subculture and counterculture is carried out. The opinions of researchers regarding the interpretation of these definitions are outlined. Within the framework of the concept, a modern view of these concepts is proposed, revealing their multifaceted nature. The issues of interaction and transformation of cultures are touched upon.*

Keywords: *culture, subculture, counterculture, mass culture, dominant culture, youth subcultures, countercultural movements.*

Introduction. "Culture", "subculture", "counterculture" are quite commonly used concepts in our time, but in the modern world they are often interpreted incorrectly. Many researchers (sociologists, cultural scientists) sooner or later turn to the problem of using such close and equally distant concepts in speech in their works. In this article, I would like to outline the main interpretations of this "trio", reveal the essence of each of them and, as the main task, draw the boundaries between them, determine the denotation and connotation of each lexeme.

There are many interpretations of the concept of "culture", analyzing and comparing each, we can identify common features characteristic of the concept, as well as discrepancies (depending on the contextual perception of the term). For the first time, the concept of "culture" appeared in the treatise on agriculture by Marcus Porcius Cato in the 2nd century BC and had a different semantic content. The treatise is devoted to the cultivation of the land, while it is important to note that when cultivating it was necessary to have a special spiritual attitude to it, the land must be liked, and only in these conditions can culture exist.

There are various interpretations of the concept of culture. According to A. Kroeber, they are divided into six main types:

- descriptive (listing everything that culture covers);
- historical (emphasis of the definition on social inheritance, traditions);
- normative (based on the idea of a way of life and ideas about values and ideals);
- psychological (emphasis on the process of adaptation to the environment);
- structural (the structural organization of culture is considered);
- genetic (the concept of culture is defined from the standpoint of its origin) [1].

Methodology. Culture is the main characteristic of human society, its development, existence, a system of values, norms, ideas, models of behavior in symbolic form, transmitted and passed on from generation to generation. The system of values is a daily guideline for a person's life, a practical attitude to objects and phenomena. This system can be a product of labor, an object of commodity exchange, or an object of art. Depending on the type of cultural subject, the following structural components of this concept are distinguished: elite or high culture (created by and for privileged groups of society, characterized by a narrow focus, spiritual aristocracy and value-semantic self-sufficiency), mass culture (adapted to the tastes and needs of the broad masses

of consumers of culture, a characteristic feature of which is high replication), folk culture (the culture of the broad masses of the people, formed from the moment of the formation of the national state, which is based on traditions and customs built on the experience of the masses and the independent activity of the peoples-bearers).

Today, culture, in a broad sense, is understood as the entire set of human activities: the skills and abilities accumulated by society, including those materialized in the form of artifacts, forms and methods of self-knowledge and self-expression, a set of clichéd codes that prescribe behavior patterns for humanity, thereby performing educational, epistemological, regulatory, value and other functions. General phenomena typical for all representatives of cultures, manifested in all societies and groups are called cultural universals. Of course, the basis laid down in the definition of "culture" is a set of socially acquired and transmitted from generation-to-generation knowledge, the core of culture is recognized as symbols, ideas, customs, traditions, norms and rules of behavior [2].

According to the British literary scholar and philosopher Terry Eagleton, culture has been narrowed to "A handful of works of art." [3] Thus, the researcher points out that culture has taken the form of artistic and intellectual works of recognized value, along with the institutions that produce, distribute and regulate them. In our opinion, culture is a "product" of the creation of humanity, but at its core lies the need of people for transformative activity. Based on all of the above and combining scientific research approaches, we will form a "modern" idea of culture.

So, culture is:

- a system of values and norms that support the socialization of society;
- a complex of ideas and their material embodiments, including the reproduction and development of man as a subject and activities;
- a system of cultural universals with structural, functional and dynamic patterns;
- a set of artifacts, knowledge, beliefs expressing the adaptation and reproduction of the human way of life. In other words, culture and any of its objects or phenomena are the result of human activity. Culture can be presented in sociological and philosophical terms as a creative activity that is a way of realizing human resources, and as a set of social institutions functioning within the framework of personal and social needs and aimed at satisfying them.

From the position of A. N. Ilyin, modern culture is reflected through the activities of communities that correlate or oppose each other, there is a complication of social organization, which is due to the growth of cultural diversity, new tendencies and trends arise that do not displace or replace the previous ones, but coexist side by side and support intercultural conflict-free [4].

For Terry Eagleton, culture is a set of potentials that have been nurtured by history and are subversive within it. In this case, culture is the unconscious flip side of civilized life, the accepted beliefs and preferences that we must become aware of in order to have an idea of what direction to work in. These two, at first glance, polar opinions are in fact far from contradicting each other, Eagleton looks inside the culture, talking about its historical and involuntary development, while not denying the creation of culture by humanity [5]. In the work "Culture Matters" Lawrence Harrison and Samuel Huntington define culture in such purely subjective terms as values, attitudes, beliefs, orientations and convictions prevailing among the members of society, and refer to the representative of anthropologists Clifford Geertz, who understands culture as a "comprehensive description" with the help of which all aspects of the life of a society are described: its practices, symbols, values, social institutions and the relationships within them⁸. The authors are also

convinced that cultural values are capable of changing, although this process is quite slow, while life attitudes change many times faster. The independent cultural spheres that have formed and are developing within the dominant culture are called subcultures. The concept of culture is closely related to the concept of subculture, which is a social reaction to social differentiation and determines the ideology of youth communities.

In the middle of the 20th century, the American sociologist Milton Gordon raises the issue of the boundaries of the term "subculture" and suggests using it to denote a set of factors that influence the development and life of an individual. In M. Gordon's interpretation, a subculture is a cluster of national culture born of a combination of individual social conditions, such as class status, region and type of residence, ethnic origin, religious affiliation, which together form a functional unity that has a holistic effect on a person and shapes his value orientations.

Along with the dominant culture, subcultures have also become widespread. By dominant culture we mean a set of values, beliefs, traditions, customs, which are followed by the majority of members of society. Subculture can be defined as a system of adapted ideas, norms, values, ideals of the dominant culture for a specific social group, expressing social protest against the phenomenon of social differentiation. Society disintegrates into many social groups, in which their own culture is gradually formed, i.e. their own system of values and rules of behavior is formed and developed [6].

Often the concept of subculture is greatly narrowed and characterized by subcultural phenomena of expression of youth subculture. Youth culture, communities in which are united by an arbitrarily chosen feature, and in a broad sense - "cultural characteristics of any group within a national culture." Each community creates a subculture with its own norms, values, beliefs, behavior patterns, with its own set of symbols, vocabulary. The existence of such groups is mainly due to certain activities (professional communities, national associations, etc.), in which their own fundamental cultural layer is born and modified, without contradicting or denying the main generally accepted culture, but "stringing" their values onto it. Developing, the bearers of subcultures develop an exclusive image, language (slang, jargon), symbols and attributes, a common ideology that is the same for all their members.

For a representative of a subculture, an image is not just an external appearance that distinguishes him, it is a demonstration of the promoted beliefs and values of the subculture. Thus, the stratification of the basic culture occurs with the simultaneous emergence of elements that fill the resulting space, adapt culture to the worldview of the created social group (association, community).

Let us compare the concepts of "culture" and "subculture": a subculture does not contradict the dominant culture, it exists within the culture, without entering into conflict with it and adding its own ideals, a subculture is a part of the culture, "a generated combination of individual social conditions" formed within a large social group and adapted to the worldview of this group. It is a little more difficult to draw a line between a subculture and a counterculture, some researchers even deny the existence of the latter, classifying countercultural phenomena as narrower forms of subculture, or simply calling such manifestations "anti-culture", "pseudo-culture", etc.

And yet it is unacceptable to identify these concepts, subculture and counterculture have different content, in both cases the basis is protest, but the subculture "protests" without denying generally accepted values, while the counterculture is completely free from global cultural restrictions, it is opposed to state policy, social ideals, seeks to transform moral values, foundations

and rules of life, replacing them with their own ideals, defending their positions and persistently seeking recognition.

According to the research of T. Roschak, counterculture originates in the USA in the post-war years (after the Second World War), when appetites were growing in the country, and "unsightly poverty" was perceived as a protest against society, ghetto-quarters began to appear. The influence of historical events on the formation of the worldview of young people was obvious, a new surge of armed conflicts in Vietnam caused a huge resonance among the public, the famous anti-war slogan "Make love, not war" thundered throughout the world and belonged to the largest countercultural movement - hippies, who declared the highest value of the world of man, and the main principle of life - love for man.

In modern society, countercultures have formed and manifest themselves in the form of sects, criminal associations, extremist organizations, often using various forms and methods of violence to achieve their goals, even often going against the state policy of the country. It is generally accepted that representatives of countercultures are from among youth associations, among them there can be both representatives of the "golden youth" and young marginals, while the latter two groups are not necessarily mutually exclusive elements. They are prone to shocking, their rebellion serves as entertainment for themselves, among the disseminated values, nonconformism, hedonism, and the cult of impulsiveness prevail. Until the mid-20th century, few people thought about trying to change the dominant culture; the very idea of cultural transformation was akin to a taboo¹⁷. Countercultural tendencies arise through various mechanisms. Firstly, they arise where the dominant culture can no longer correspond to the realities of the new era. Therefore, they appear, denying outdated forms and affirming new ones. Secondly, the need for self-affirmation is one of the driving factors in the formation of social countercultural tendencies.

Results and discussion. Based on the concepts discussed earlier, let us generalize. Counterculture is:

- a movement that contradicts official norms and rules, which is completely free from the dominance of generally accepted cultural norms and rules, individual and innovative in its essence;
- a certain set of guidelines and beliefs, which is based on opposition to the values of the dominant culture, with the introduction of a new cultural core;
- a destructive youth movement that distorts social reality.

Counterculture does not always need to be presented with a negative connotation. For example, the hippie counterculture movement rediscovered social ecology as a critical force, causing a reevaluation of the growth economy, the consumer lifestyle, and anthropocentric science.

The main functions of counterculture are psychological: raising the status of a movement representative in his own eyes and within this movement, his attempt to escape from public control, thus, the period of stay within the framework and conditions of counterculture becomes a period of personality formation, his acceptance or rejection by society and society. Theodore Roschak wrote that it is most likely even incorrect to talk about participation in the movement as membership, it was more a conceptual system that penetrated the consciousness and became the work of a lifetime, and perhaps even its meaning. In the desire to eradicate countercultural movements, he saw a sign that in the view of classical communities it poses a threat, although over time the tension of the public has subsided to a "complacently dismissive" attitude.

Summarizing what has been said in this article, we note the following. The dominant culture is the embodiment of social norms, rules, and values accepted in society, the dominance of

which was achieved through the control of social institutions. Subculture is part of the national culture.

Cultures with transformed values and rules of conduct for a specific social group. Counterculture is a culture whose values and norms oppose those that dominate in society. All of them are closely interconnected and dependent on each other. These phenomena are transformed over time, flowing from one cultural state to another. Subcultures also reflect the values and norms of society, but somewhat adapt them for a specific social group, introducing new ideas into implementation.

Conclusion. When these new ideas, which do not contradict the traditions established in the group at all, begin to seep into other societies, the subculture expands to mass culture, moving to the same level as the dominant one and ceasing to be a subculture. Counterculture does not claim to be universal, but, again, being a set of subcultural elements, it forms a core that initially has a protest function, but which over time may well be accepted by society, which is associated with the dynamism and variability of the latter. Thus, the concepts under consideration are in a cyclical dependence on each other, and their norms and values, changing in accordance with the currents of time, can undergo metamorphoses, which leads to the substitution of concepts and modifications of cultural, subcultural and countercultural phenomena.

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